
Repository Resilience in Practice

Findings and Strategies from a Community in Crisis

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Executive Summary

Data are integral to daily life, underpinning weather forecasting, disaster response, healthcare, transportation, education, and evidence-based policymaking. Yet the worldwide repositories that store and provide access to these data are under growing pressure, from funding instability and political disruption to workforce loss and technical fragility, often simultaneously and without adequate support. When data repositories are weakened, censored, or removed, there are harmful consequences beyond the loss of information.

This project, *Building Resilience of Data Repositories During Periods of Crisis*, examined how repositories experience and withstand disruption. Using Repository Crisis Scorecards (RCS), focus groups, and surveys, the project gathered insights from repository administrators, technical staff, data users, and citizen archivists across more than 14 countries. Findings reveal a consistent pattern: repositories are generally well-prepared for routine operations but significantly less prepared for systemic shocks. Three interconnected, central threats emerged: funding and policy disruption, workforce and expertise loss, and infrastructure and access failures.

Everyone who needs reliable data has a role to play, from repository administrators and funders to policymakers, researchers, and the communities who depend on it daily for decisions about development and emergency responses. A practical set of actions are outlined, informed by community feedback, to strengthen repository resilience. The strategies that proved most effective share a common thread: they reduce dependence on any single funder, person, institution, or system. These strategies include diversifying funding streams, building redundant and distributed infrastructure, investing in stable and well-supported staff, and establishing crisis response plans before they are needed. Treating data repositories not as optional project outputs but as essential public infrastructure, worthy of the same sustained investment as roads or public health systems, is the necessary foundation for a resilient data ecosystem.

Data Repositories at Risk

Data and information stored via data repositories are increasingly exposed to risks that threaten their ability to remain accessible, recoverable, and useful over time. With our world more interconnected than ever, many critical decisions rely on data repositories. These provide the foundation for evidence-based policymaking, disaster preparedness, and international research collaboration (Zhang et al. 2024). When repositories fail, the consequences can reach far beyond a single institution or agency, impacting public access to reliable information.

Data disruptions are becoming more visible and consequential. At the start of 2025, over 8,000 federal web pages were removed from government sites (Singer 2025). This purge included the removal of health, environmental, and educational data used daily by researchers and communities. Data.gov, the official open data portal for the United States (U.S.) government, held over 300,000 datasets accumulated over 15 years. The site received over a million monthly visits (Meyer 2014; data.gov 2025), demonstrating the importance of this data. Yet, nearly 3,400 of the data.gov datasets had been removed in early 2025, including repositories tracking drought and food insecurity in 30 countries like the Famine Early Warning Systems Network (Grown and Dews 2025; Palmer 2025; Stone and Simmons-Duffin 2025). While some data have been restored, the process has been inconsistent and opaque (Stone and Huang 2025), creating uncertainty about the long-term availability, reliability, and integrity of U.S. federal data.

Beyond the political pressures that have led to vanishing data sets, data repositories face a compounding set of pressures. Funding and staffing losses have strained repository operations (Nature Geoscience 2025), while repositories are being asked to support growing data volumes, more complex model outputs (Schuster et al. 2023), diverse user needs, and faster response times. Simultaneously, disasters, hazards, cyber risks, evolving technologies such as artificial

intelligence, and organizational instability are making it challenging for repositories to remain reliable over time (Kirkwood et al. 2023; Lin et al. 2020; Thorsheim 2013; Merrill 1943). These challenges are often compounded by declining budgets (Ahern et al. 2020), creating a widening gap between what repositories are expected to do and what they are resourced to support.

Data repositories make it possible to verify findings, reproduce studies, and build on prior work; but only if the data remains accessible long enough to be used. Without active maintenance and care, that access is far from guaranteed. One study reviewing 516 papers found that data availability drops 17% post-publication, simply because contact information becomes out of date or storage media becomes inaccessible or obsolete (Vines et al. 2014). This makes it increasingly difficult for other researchers to verify findings, access data, or build on prior work. The repositories designed to prevent this kind of loss face their own vulnerability.

"We're going to see a loss of information that will make the burning of the library of Alexandria look like nothing. And it's going to happen before anybody notices."

- Focus Group Participant

Despite how consequential the loss of this data can be, limited studies exist on research repositories shutting down and what happens to the data they hold (Boyd 2021). A 2023 study that did examine this challenge identified 191 closed repositories (roughly 6.2% of the 3,069 registered facilities at the time of the study). These closures are often occurring without permanent data migration, leaving gaps in our scientific understanding (Strecker et al. 2023). The gaps in data access, combined with the challenges of information lost post-publication, create problems for those hoping to make science inquiries or critical decisions based on available knowledge.

Numerous groups have recently mobilized in response to data disruptions. Academic librarians are creating resources for preserving endangered datasets, and citizen archivists are dedicating countless hours to data rescue and preservation (Galvin 2025; Palmer 2025). These efforts underscore the current fragility of data repositories yet the depth of commitment to protecting them. But emergency response is not resilience. True resilience means repositories are built to withstand disruption, not just recover afterward. In an era of increased uncertainty ranging from cyberattacks to staffing and budget shortfalls, it is more critical than ever to assess the suite of systems we have in place and focus scientific community efforts and discussions toward actionable solutions.

This paper shares findings from *Building Resilience of Data Repositories During Periods of Crisis*, a project focused on understanding how disruptions affect data repositories and the people who rely on them. The project engaged those who use, contribute to, manage, or support data rescue and preservation efforts, gathering insights on the real-world impacts of disruption and the strategies that are already making a difference. These insights are elevated through participants' quotes and perspectives shared via callout boxes. Three interconnected threats to repository resilience are highlighted: funding and political disruption, workforce and expertise loss, and infrastructure access. The goal of the project is not only to draw attention to these challenges but to also make the case that data repository resilience is achievable.

Participant Perspectives: A System on the Verge of Collapse

Our data infrastructure is far more fragile than it appears from the outside. The repositories many of us depend on are running with thin margins. We patch things together with volunteer labor and limited funding, but there is rarely a plan for what happens when those run out.

It feels like an aging structure held together by interconnected parts. Remove one piece (e.g., a key staff member, a funding source, a supporting service) and the consequences ripple outward in ways that are hard to predict and harder to reverse. Once these systems collapse, what was lost may be gone permanently. And most people will not notice until they go looking for something that is no longer there.

Understanding Repository Resilience

Defining Resilience

In the context of this project, we define **repository resilience as the ability to make data accessible, recoverable, and useful under both normal operations and crisis conditions**. A resilient repository is one that can survive a funding cut, recover from a natural disaster, or outlast a change in institutional priorities without losing the data or the trust of the people who depend on it.

Measuring Resilience: Repository Crisis Scorecards (RCS)

Recognizing that challenges surrounding data repository resilience had grown urgent, a working group within Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP) developed the Repository Crisis Scorecards (RCS) in April 2025 (Gum et al. 2025). The RCS was designed as a practical, self-assessment tool: a way for anyone connected to a data repository to evaluate resilience under both normal operations and crisis conditions. Since its launch, the RCS has been downloaded over 3,000 times and featured at several science conference discussions, reflecting growing national and international concern about data vulnerability.

The RCS evaluates repositories across seven categories, covering everything from metadata and technical infrastructure to governance and staffing. Users receive a composite resilience score as well as a breakdown by category, so they can identify specific areas of strength and vulnerability. Foundational tools like the National Digital Stewardship Alliance Levels (NDSA)¹, Trustworthy Repositories Audit Certification/ISO 16363 (TRAC/ISO 16363)², Digital Repository Audit Method Based on Risk Assessment (DRAMBORA)³, and the transparent, responsible, user focus, sustainable, and technology principles (TRUST Principles)⁴ provide guidance for data preservation and repository trustworthiness. However, no existing initiative currently combines scenario-based resilience scoring with empirical, user-informed analysis and actionable recommendations. The RCS fills that gap, building on the foundation that existing frameworks have established. RCS outputs provide easily comparable scores evaluating different aspects of resilience, accompanied

¹ NDSA Levels of Digital Preservation helps practitioners build or assess a digital preservation program through a staged matrix of practices. <https://www.ndsa.org/publications/levels-of-digital-preservation/>

² TRAC was developed as a checklist for trustworthy repositories and was later formalized as ISO 16363, the audit and certification standard for trustworthy digital repositories. <https://preservedigitalohio.com/standards/trusted-digital-repositories-iso-16363/index.html>

³ DRAMBORA focuses on identifying and documenting repository risks, then mapping them to organizational priorities and resources. <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/tools/drambora>

⁴ TRUST is a values-oriented framing concept to facilitate discussion and implementation of best practice in digital preservation. [Lin et al. \(2020\)](#)

by how-to guidance on overcoming resilience gaps that is informed by both community experience and the broader literature.

About This Project

This project, *Building Resilience of Data Repositories During Periods of Crisis*, builds on the 2025 RCS by enhancing the self-assessment tool, gathering community insights on disruptions and resilience strategies through focus groups and surveys, and translating those findings into actionable recommendations for the broader research ecosystem. The project was guided by five core questions:

- How have disruptions in data access affected the ability to conduct high-quality and impactful research?
- How have disruptions in data access affected communities' ability to respond to natural disasters or other crises?
- How has the loss of personnel impacted data collection, curation, and dissemination?
- What practices or strategies were in place that effectively mitigated the recent disruptions?
- What practices and supports are needed to increase repository resilience and mitigate the impacts of future disruptions?

Participants recruited to the project included repository administrators, scientific and technical domain experts, repository data users (e.g., researchers, first responders, policy makers), and citizen archivists (e.g., volunteers supporting data rescue efforts). Each of these groups has direct experience relevant to repositories and some have experience with data repository failures or data repositories under threat.

The findings and recommendations shared reflect the collective experience of those who engaged directly in evaluating a data repository via the RCS, a focus group, or survey. These findings are complemented by literature and recent news articles. The sections that follow begin with findings from the RCS responses on the current state of repository resilience, then move into three major themes that connect the challenges facing repositories, their impacts, and possible strategies for addressing and mitigating disruptions and data loss. The paper then offers audience-specific considerations and closes with future directions, including reflections on who was missing from this work (*refer to Appendices A-E for details about the project approach and more detailed results*).

Patterns in Repository Resilience

The RCS submissions collected during this project provide the first empirical snapshot of how repositories around the world assess their own resilience. The results reveal a field that is largely holding steady in routine conditions, but with important vulnerabilities beneath the surface.

Across 44 RCS submissions in 10 countries, a clear pattern emerged: repositories are generally well-prepared for routine operations, but less prepared for the unexpected.

Of the 44 RCS submissions received during the project across ten countries (i.e., United States, Germany, United Kingdom, Australia, India, Estonia, Netherlands, France, Lithuania, and Taiwan), the majority of repositories scored within moderate resilience range (Figure 1). No repositories self classified as low resilience overall (Figure 1). The results suggest that basic practices may be widely in place, while truly robust resilience remains the exception rather than the rule. A meaningful subset (27%, N=44) demonstrated high resilience, suggesting that strong resilience practices are achievable when appropriate steps are taken.

FIGURE 1. Distribution of repository resilience ratings across RCS submissions (low, moderate, and high; N=44).

Sections of the RCS measuring day-to-day technical operations (Repository Infrastructure, Routine Operations, Software, and Cybersecurity), scored high on average (Table 1). Most telling, no crisis scenario achieved an average rating of high preparedness (Table 2), indicating a systemic gap in contingency planning for data repositories and an area that should be explored more to boost repository resilience. Critical pockets of vulnerability were also revealed in network redundancy and collaboration, disaster preparedness, and infrastructure robustness, as these areas scored in the moderate range (Table 1). Taken together, these results of the RCS suggest that **repositories are well-prepared for regular operations, but less prepared for systemic shocks or disruptions.**

Table 1. Average resilience rating category (low, moderate, or high) for each RCS section, based on all submissions (N=44)

RCS Section	Average Resiliency Rating
Cybersecurity and Access Control	High
Repository Infrastructure	High
Routine Operations	High
Software	High
Dataset Replication	Moderate
Network	Moderate
Sustainability	Moderate

Across subject areas, RCS scores clustered within a narrow 9-point range near the high end of moderate resilience (Table 3). This consistency suggests that repository resilience is shaped more by infrastructure, governance, and funding than by disciplinary differences.

A notable pattern was that computer and information sciences and interdisciplinary research indicated the lowest concentration of high resilience ratings (Figure 2), which may say less about their practices and more about their awareness. Computer information sciences, for example, may be more familiar with the complexities and challenges of data repository systems, thus rating themselves lower.

Table 2. Average preparedness rating category (low, moderate, or high) for each crisis scenario, based on all submissions (N=44)

Crisis Scenario	Average Preparedness Rating
Cyberattack	Moderate
Defunding	Moderate
Loss of Personnel	Moderate
Natural Disaster	Moderate

Table 3. Average resilience score by subject area across all submissions (N=44). Note: Scores of 0-43 = low resilience; 43-86 = moderate resilience, and 86-129 = high resilience

Subject	Average Resilience Score
Earth & Environment	78.8
Social Science	78.2
Humanities	76.7
Arts & Culture	75.9
Health & Medicine	75.2
Computer Information	74.7
Physical Science	74.7
Engineering & Tech	73.4
Life Science	72.8
Interdiscipline Research	71.8
Math & Statistics	70.0

FIGURE 2. Distribution of repository resilience ratings (low, moderate, and high) by subject area (N=44).

Scores varied depending on who completed the RCS, in a pattern that tracks closely with how different people experience repositories. Data repository users reported the highest average resilience scores, followed by scientific and technical staff, repository administrators, and citizen archivists (Figure 3, Figure 4). The variation in scores likely reflects differences in proximity to repository systems. Data users may experience repositories primarily through successful access and use cases, leading to higher perceived resilience while administrators and technical staff are more aware of infrastructure limitations, staffing constraints, and sustainability risks. This awareness may contribute to slightly lower scores. Citizen archivists, who often engage with repositories during failure or recovery scenarios, reported substantially lower resilience scores, roughly a 10-point gap from the next group (Figure 3).

FIGURE 3. Average resilience score by respondent type (N=44). *Note: Scores of 0-43 = low resilience; 43-86 = moderate resilience, and 86-129 = high resilience.*

FIGURE 4. Distribution of RCS submissions by respondent type (N=44)

Taken together, the RCS results point to a community that has built a solid foundation but has not yet broken through to true resilience. Repositories demonstrate strong data management practices; metadata, documentation, and data quality protocols are broadly in place. But the systems that ensure data remains accessible when something goes wrong (e.g., continuity agreements, crisis plans, diverse funding, external partnerships) lag behind. The result is a ceiling effect, where repositories achieve baseline resilience, but face barriers to advancing further. These barriers likely include: funding constraints, staffing limitations, and lack of formalized partnerships or long-term planning. Challenges illuminated in the RCS repository self-assessment were also common in the focus group and survey, and together they shape the three themes that follow.

RCS Feedback and Improvements

Throughout the project, feedback on the RCS was collected alongside the broader focus group and survey data, providing an opportunity to assess and improve the tool itself. In response, Version 2 of the RCS was developed and is now publicly available (Sutton-Kennedy, et al. 2026), implementing normalized scoring to 100% for easier interpretation, a refined question structure for clarity, and improved definitions and examples. Respondents now receive a personalized report with actionable recommendations grounded in the findings of this project, directly connecting self-assessment results to strategies for strengthening resilience. The RCS remains a practical and accessible tool for any repository looking to evaluate and strengthen its resilience. A full summary of participant feedback and recommendations for future development are outlined in Appendix E.

What Repositories Are Experiencing: Project Findings

Theme One: Funding and Policy Disruptions

Challenges

Data repositories are rarely independent of broader organizational and financial factors. They are embedded within institutions, and those institutions depend on funding and governance stability to keep them operating effectively. When budgets are cut or political priorities shift, repositories suffer. These two forces (financial and political) are distinct in how they operate but similar in their effect: both can make data that was accessible yesterday, unavailable today.

"I think funding stability is the existential threat."

- Focus Group Participant

Funding instability emerged as one of the clearest structural threats to repository resilience from focus group and survey participants. For many, it was not just a hypothetical concern about the future but was their current reality. Repositories were described as often operating well when a project is newly funded, then becoming increasingly vulnerable when grants end or institutional priorities shift. The underlying problem is not simply insufficient money; it is the lack of predictable, sustainable funding that supports preservation, maintenance, staffing, and planning over time.

56% of focus groups | **64%** of surveys cited operational and financial strain as a threat to repository resilience.

Participants were clear: the impact of funding loss is broad and cascading for data repositories. The most direct consequence described is that when a repository loses funding during operation, the workflows relied upon by researchers, emergency managers, and policymakers are disrupted. Recent cuts to the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), outlined in a Nature GeoScience 2025 editorial, highlighted the impacts of reduced funding, which led to understaffing and the degradation of data critical to hurricane forecasting, weather prediction, and atmospheric and ocean observations. These cuts include NOAA data critical to emergency management, informing the insurance industry and rebuilding after weather disasters. The most harmful reported consequences included repositories closing entirely and the datasets they hold becoming orphaned with no clear path to recovery. Beyond these immediate effects, participants pointed to longer-term effects such as staffing reductions that erode institutional knowledge, declining user trust in platforms that have become unreliable, and the gradual loss of datasets that can never be reconstructed (Nature GeoScience 2025).

Political pressure and policy shifts also create uncertainty for repositories by making access contingent on changing institutional or governmental priorities. In a third of focus groups, participants described disruptions arising from government shutdowns, policy decisions, or institutional changes that removed access to datasets, eliminated support, or altered data availability. Unlike funding cuts, which tend to erode capacity gradually, politically motivated disruptions can be immediate and targeted. Data that existed one day is simply unavailable the next.

“In terms of policy, what can you do to prevent it? Nothing. We're completely at the point for policy makers that this is never going to be a make or break issue when it comes to elections. Nobody's going to say, but “what is your position on research data repositories?”...”

- Focus Group Participant, when asked what supports, policies, or practices are most needed to improve repository resilience and reduce the impact of future disruptions

The removal of the Social Vulnerability Index (a widely used tool that helps emergency managers identify communities most at risk during disasters) illustrates how quickly a political decision can eliminate data that communities and researchers depend on (Smith 2025). This removal did not occur in isolation. HIV treatment guidance, youth health data, EJSscreen, and climate risk tools from the National Climate Assessment were among the many datasets removed or discontinued in the same period (Smith 2025).

The impacts share some common ground with funding loss: users lose confidence, researchers hesitate to rely on platforms whose content may change without warning, and the evidence base that scholars and practitioners depend on becomes less stable. Political disruption can also have cumulative effects when political decisions lead agencies to withdraw support, triggering contract terminations and funding cuts that compound the damage. In 2025, a series of politically driven directives led NASA to terminate its contract with the team operating the Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center (SEDAC), putting over six terabytes of data at risk that had bridged Earth and social science research communities (Diggs and Parsons 2026; de Sherbinin 2026). Community efforts ultimately helped relocate much of that data, but this example highlights one current challenge for building resilient, trusted systems.

“But if our institution's budget goes away, if God forbid our institution closes...then all of humanity has lost access to that piece of our human prehistory which may not exist anywhere else in the world and may not be replicable.”

- Focus Group Participant, in reference to digital artifacts only available in institution's collection

Strategies

Focus groups (89%) pointed to sustainable and dedicated infrastructure funding as the most important strategy for future resilience. This includes moving away from project-based funding to stable, long-term support models paired with governance structures that can survive leadership changes and shifting institutional priorities. Diversifying funding streams so that no single funder, grant, or budget line can destabilize a repository was also a priority, raised by 44% of focus groups. Similarly, 67% emphasized the importance of maintaining redundant and distributed data infrastructure so that data can survive even if a primary repository fails or loses institutional support.

“Digital preservation is the thing we've been doing for a long time and we know what to do. We just need the resources to make it happen.”

- Focus Group Participant

The strategies that work share a common thread: they reduce dependence on any single funder, institution, or political climate. The table below outlines the key funding and policy resilience strategies drawn from the RCS, each of which addresses a specific vulnerability identified in this section (Table 5).

Table 5. Strategies, implications, and impacts for funding and policy resilience from the RCS

Strategy	What It Means	Why It Matters
Diversify funding	Pursue funding from multiple sources and avoid over-dependence on any single funder, grant cycle, or institutional budget line	A single funding loss should not be able to shut down a repository
Boost international or external replication	Maintain an independent copy of data in a different country or with a partner institution, so data can survive national-level disruptions or policy changes	Protects against politically motivated removals and institutional collapse
Establish crisis support agreements	Create formal or informal agreements with partner institutions that can provide emergency hosting, staffing support, or other assistance during a crisis	Ensures repositories are not alone when disruption hits
Embed institutional commitment	Secure and document formal commitments to the repository's continued operation from host organizations, parent agencies, or governing bodies	Reduces vulnerability to leadership changes and shifting priorities
Ensure Data Portability	Ensure data can be exported and migrated to another system or platform without loss of content, metadata, or provenance	Prevents data from being locked into a single platform or institution

Ultimately, **long-term repository resilience depends on treating data repositories as public infrastructure** (e.g., roads, public health systems) worthy of sustained investment, despite limited understanding of data stewardship among many decision makers.

Participant Perspectives: *Valuation by Society*

Most people do not think about where data comes from or what it takes to keep it accessible. The systems that make data available (e.g., repositories, archives, data centers) run quietly in the background, and that invisibility works against them. We see it constantly: longitudinal data collections disrupted mid-stream, maintenance budgets cut, institutional knowledge allowed to walk out the door, and valuable datasets increasingly concentrated in private hands with no public accountability.

What concerns us most is not any single loss but the pattern. Data infrastructure tends to be taken for granted until it fails, and by the time people notice it is gone, recovery is far more expensive than preservation ever would have been. A shift in how society values this work is not just desirable. It is necessary.

Theme Two: Workforce and Expertise Loss

Challenges

Data repositories are not just systems, they are sustained by people. Behind every data repository are individuals who maintain systems, manage metadata, enforce data quality standards, and carry years of institutional knowledge about how things work, why decisions were made, and what to do when something goes wrong. That knowledge is not just valuable, it is often irreplaceable.

"Some systems are running with people on renewable three-month contracts. So it's inherent that the system's going to fail if the critical staff are all on short-term contracts."

- Focus Group Participant

Loss of personnel emerged as one of the most important drivers of data repository fragility across focus groups and the survey. Staff departures can interrupt maintenance, delay fixes, reduce user support, and create single points of failure when technical or curatorial knowledge is concentrated with one person or a very small team. The National Center for Education Statistics, for example, can no longer provide timely or complete datasets to support evidence-based decision-making in schools, not because the data does not exist, but because the staff needed to maintain and release it are gone (Grown and Dews 2025).

"I've been doing this for about 30 years and, over that time, I have had hundreds of different staff members leave ... We get some people that are really dedicated to our mission, who stay a long time, but we have a lot of short-term turnover with entry-level software engineers."

- Focus Group Participant

Documentation helps, but it has limits that are easy to underestimate. Written procedures capture how things work under normal conditions, the expected workflows, the standard operating procedures, and the routine tasks. What they cannot capture is the judgment that comes from years of experience: knowing which exception to a rule matters, how to troubleshoot a problem that was never anticipated, or how to navigate a relationship with a partner institution that took years to build. When an experienced staff member leaves, that gap cannot be filled by a manual.

Participant Perspectives: *Losing a Unicorn*

We call them unicorns; the people who somehow combine deep scientific domain knowledge with data science skills, software development, web development, and user experience design all in one role. They are rare because that combination takes years to develop, and they are often the ones holding a repository together in ways that only become visible when they are gone.

When they leave, we feel it immediately. Hiring managers face impossible tradeoffs: do you prioritize domain knowledge or technical skill? Which skills can be taught, and which are essential from day one? There is no easy answer, because the positions and career pathways that would attract and retain people like this do not really exist in government or academia. The structures were simply never built for this kind of work. What we are left with is an uncomfortable truth: some of what walks out the door when a unicorn leaves cannot be written down, transferred, or replaced on a hiring timeline. It is just gone. And the repository carries that loss forward in ways that are not always visible until something breaks.

Focus groups and surveys painted a consistent picture of repositories stretched thin. Small teams, volunteer labor, and single points of expertise were among the most frequently cited sources of fragility in focus groups (Table 6). The survey data reinforced this, with participants reporting interrupted operations, reduced user support, delayed system upgrades, and breakdowns in data quality as direct consequences of workforce loss. Perhaps most concerning were the longer-term effects such as reduced compliance with data standards, erosion of user trust, and increased sustainability risk.

Table 6. Impacts of workforce and expertise loss reported within each focus group and by survey participants

Impact	% of Focus Groups (N=9)	% of Surveys (N=26)
Loss of institutional knowledge	33%	25%
Operational disruptions and reduced service capacity	33%	23%
Increased fragility due to lack of redundancy	33%	19%
Workforce instability and hiring challenges	33%	–
Reliance on volunteer or overextended labor	44%	–

“There are only two of us who are working on it on a voluntary basis and ensuring that the service is running, responding to any queries.”

- Focus Group Participant

Personnel loss ultimately threatens more than day-to-day operations. It undermines technical reliability, governance capacity, and the long-term survival of repositories in ways that are difficult to reverse. The people who maintain repositories are also the people who understand what the data means, how it was collected, and what its limitations are, because that knowledge does not transfer automatically to a new system or a new team. Recent challenges for systems often coincide with sharp federal workforce

reductions (Shao and Wu 2025), removing institutional knowledge, and limiting the ability to maintain or release critical data products. The result of this personnel loss is an unprecedented erosion of trust in the information that remains. The data still exists but lacks the expert stewardship needed to ensure it is current, complete, and reliable at precisely the moment when public access to trustworthy information matters most.

Throughout the focus group discussions and surveys, respondents highlighted the challenges with direct examples of staffing turnover, overworked teams with minimal resources, and fully taking on work as a volunteer. Diggs and Parsons (2026) highlight this expertise loss and the current challenge noting that workforce and trust networks are the most fragile elements of resilience. The authors call on the community to act, framing the solution as a professional and ethical challenge (Diggs and Parsons 2026). Stable, well-compensated positions attract and retain talented repository staff. Short-term contracts, volunteer arrangements, and under-resourced teams all create fragility that make repositories vulnerable. **Treating data stewardship as a legitimate, valued profession and not simply a supporting role for scientists is both a cultural and financial commitment.**

Strategies

The strategies participants identified for addressing workforce fragility share a common thread: they distribute knowledge and responsibility across people and systems so that no single departure creates a crisis. Treating data stewardship as a profession with stable, well-compensated positions rather than short-term contracts and volunteer arrangements is key.

Cross-training was one of the most consistently cited strategies, raised by focus group and survey participants. When more than one person understands each critical system, workflow, and curatorial process, the repository is no longer dependent on any individual's continued presence. Cross-training does not eliminate the value of specialized expertise, yet it ensures that expertise is not locked inside a single person.

Succession planning takes that logic a step further by making the transition explicit before it is needed. Rather than scrambling when a key staff member departs, repositories with succession plans already know who assumes which responsibilities, where the data will go if funding is lost, and what the handoff process looks like. The difference in outcomes can be stark.

"This year, I have seen that repositories that had a succession plan have done the best. Ones who have been scrambling to put together a plan have done the worst."

- Survey Respondent

Completing and maintaining metadata and data management plans rounds out the workforce resilience picture. These are not substitutes for people, but they ensure that when staff do change, the knowledge needed to find, understand, and use the data does not change with them. Complete metadata and documented data management plans mean that a new team member or a partner institution is not starting from scratch. The table below outlines the key workforce and expertise loss strategies drawn from the RCS, each of which addresses a specific vulnerability identified in this section (Table 7).

Table 7. Strategies, implications, and impacts to combat workforce and expertise from the RCS

Strategy	What It Means	Why It Matters
Cross-training	Train multiple staff members on each critical system and workflow so no single person's departure creates an operational gap	Distributes knowledge across the team so the repository can continue functioning when staff change
Succession planning	Document who assumes key responsibilities if leadership or senior staff depart, and where data will go if funding is lost	Ensures transitions are managed rather than scrambled, reducing the risk of data loss during disruption
Complete metadata	Ensure metadata records are complete, standardized, and independently accessible	Allows data to be found, understood, and reused even when the staff who created it are no longer available
Data management plans	Maintain documented plans describing how data is collected, stored, managed, and preserved over time	Provides continuity of understanding across staff changes and ensures institutional knowledge is not lost with personnel

It is clear throughout these discussions and within the literature that the workforce must be addressed to achieve data repository resilience. Of course this workforce challenge links to budgets and data users citing and boosting repositories as well, but no amount of current recovery of data sets will address the fundamental problem of needing and retaining people. The data repository community should strategize ways to grapple with this challenge.

Theme Three: Infrastructure and Access Failures

Challenges

Funding and workforce pressures are often intertwined with other challenges, making technical systems more fragile too. But even well-funded repositories with strong teams face technical threats that can disrupt access without warning. A cyberattack can compromise data integrity or force systems offline. Hardware failures can corrupt or destroy records. A failed platform migration can make years of data temporarily or permanently inaccessible. Outdated file formats can render information unreadable as the software that created them becomes obsolete. What these failures share is a common consequence: the data may still exist, but users cannot access it.

"One of the big risk factors is where there are big, well-funded institutions...And I think what recent events have exposed is that even big and well-funded single points of failure, are single points of failure."

- Focus Group Participant

Beyond hardware and migration failures, repositories face an evolving range of malicious and disruptive threats that can compromise data integrity and overwhelm systems without warning. Cybersecurity incidents (including ransomware attacks, DDoS incidents, and unauthorized access attempts) represent some of the most serious risks, with the potential to force systems offline, corrupt records, or expose sensitive data. Bot scraping poses a growing challenge. A 2025 COAR survey confirms that AI bots scraping repositories for model training data are driving up hosting and maintenance costs, forcing organizations to invest in additional servers, increase staff monitoring, and in some cases raise service fees (Shearer and Walk 2025; Weinberg 2025). Although the scraping is not always malicious in intent, even AI systems conducting automated harvesting to preserve or collect data at scale can generate the same disruptive load as a deliberate attack.

Focus group and survey participants described infrastructure and access failures as directly undermining their ability to do timely, reliable work. When systems go down, workflows stop, and key datasets become unavailable precisely when they are most needed. Participants also highlighted that technical disruptions erode confidence in repositories over time. Once a platform has experienced an outage or a security incident, users begin to question whether the data it holds is complete, whether it has been tampered with, and whether access will be there when they need it. Concerns about cybersecurity were especially prominent, particularly around cloud environments where hacks and unauthorized access raise additional ethical and privacy questions.

When a repository's technical infrastructure is disrupted, as occurred after Hurricane Helene (September 2024) struck Asheville, North Carolina, access to critical data can fail. NOAA's National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI), the federal repository that publicly shares global environmental and weather data, lost connectivity and stopped receiving data for weeks, leaving its archive inaccessible to users (Alder 2024, NCEI 2024). Much of the data found on

NCEI, including data from the seafloor to the surface of the Sun as well as historical records dating back to the 1700s, inform decisions across agriculture, energy, transportation, water resources, and national security (Alder 2024). Although staff and data holdings were unharmed, the outage prevented acceptance of observations from at least 275 data streams, and NCEI warned that some observational data might be unrecoverable (Alder 2024, Zhong 2024). Connectivity resumed a month later, but processing the backlog was expected to take up to three months. This breakdown illustrates how infrastructure disruptions at a single repository can create a multiweek barrier to accessing critical data at precisely the moment it is needed most.

Data loss clearly has consequences beyond a single project, outage or incident. When access fails, researchers may lose irreplaceable longitudinal or environmental data, historical context, and the ability to reproduce or extend prior work. Disruptions also create openings for misinformation when authoritative sources become unreliable or unavailable, weakening the evidence base that scholars and practitioners depend on. Survey participants were also candid about reputational consequences, highlighting concerns about how repository disruptions affect future collaborations, funding opportunities, and confidence in the integrity of the data itself.

"The supply chains for providing technical equipment are all extremely fragile. There needs to be more future-looking folks identifying these issues and trying to mitigate them now versus later when it's going to be actually problematic. A deep appraisal is one of the ways that we can at least know what we have and what deserves those extra resources and the extra costs to preserve."

- Focus Group Participant

Participants raised concerns that burdens of disruption are not evenly distributed. Communities with fewer resources, lower digital access, or greater dependence on public data are often affected first and most severely. The removal of EJScreen, the EPA's environmental justice mapping tool that allowed communities, planners, and advocates to identify neighborhoods facing the highest combined burden of environmental risk and social vulnerability, illustrates this directly (Smith 2025). Tools like EJScreen were built specifically to surface the needs of vulnerable populations and inform decisions about where protections and resources are most needed. Federal data loss more broadly is creating significant challenges for local communities and governments who depend on public data to plan for disease outbreaks, disasters, crime prevention, transportation, and housing. When they disappear, the communities they were designed to serve lose visibility at exactly the moment they can least afford to. The loss of historical or institutional data compounds this inequity by weakening the evidence used to understand risk, plan interventions, and evaluate outcomes over time, leaving already vulnerable communities with even less to work with. **Access to data is not just a research concern. It is a public interest issue**, and the people least able to absorb the loss are consistently the ones who feel it most.

Strategies

Technical fragility rarely exists in isolation. It is usually a symptom of the broader systemic weaknesses described in the previous themes of funding, governance, and workforce. But even when funding and workforce challenges are addressed, repositories still need deliberate technical strategies to withstand disruption. Repositories that combine infrastructure redundancy with workforce planning and governance support are better positioned to withstand disruptions and recover more quickly.

Redundancy was the most consistently cited technical strategy, raised by 67% of focus groups and 25% of survey respondents. The idea is that no single copy of data, no single system, and no single location should be the only option. This means maintaining multiple copies of data across geographically separated facilities on separate power grids, keeping at least one copy offline or air-gapped to protect against cyberattacks, and storing data across multiple media types so that a single technology failure cannot destroy everything. Redundancy does not eliminate risk but ensures that when something fails, as it eventually will, the failure is survivable.

"It's not always easy to find the long term place for the data because most of the repositories are time limited in their funding."

- Focus Group Participant

Standardization practices are also seen as important for reducing dependence on any one system, format, or person thereby improving infrastructure and data access overall. Using open, non-proprietary data formats, persistent identifiers (such as DOIs), and interoperable metadata standards reduce the risk that data becomes inaccessible as technologies evolve. This standardization reduces dependence on any one system, format, or institution, making it easier to migrate data between systems when necessary, without losing critical context or provenance (Digital Preservation Handbook 2015).

"Migration is the only impending disruption that we can plan on reliably; but we can only plan for it in a vague sense because each platform is different. Having a standard for some basic fields would alleviate some of this pressure and also make data rescue easier."

- Focus Group Participant

Crisis response planning closes the gap between having resilient infrastructure and knowing what to do when it is tested. Focus group and survey participants noted that contingency plans have never been formalized for many repositories, which means that when a crisis hits, decisions are being made under pressure without a clear framework. A written, tested plan that defines responsibilities, escalation procedures, minimum service levels, and communication protocols with

users and partners transforms crisis response from improvisation into preparation. Post-incident reviews after any significant disruption then turn experience into institutional learning, strengthening the repository's ability to respond the next time.

The table below outlines the key infrastructure and access resilience strategies drawn from the RCS, each of which addresses a specific vulnerability identified in this section (Table 8).

Table 8. Strategies, implications, and impacts to boost infrastructure and access from the RCS

Strategy	What It Means	Why It Matters
Diversify media and replicate	Maintain independent copies at geographically separated facilities, keep at least one offline or air-gapped copy, and store across multiple media types	Ensures no single failure can destroy all copies
Test backups	Maintain a regular backup schedule and actively test restoration procedures	Discovering a backup does not work during a crisis is too late; regular testing confirms recovery is actually possible before it is needed
Evaluate vendor risk	Assess and manage risks from third-party vendors, cloud providers, and supply chains the repository depends on	External dependencies can fail or change without warning, creating unexpected vulnerabilities
Use open formats	Store data in open, non-proprietary formats readable without specialized software	Protects against data becoming inaccessible as software is discontinued or technologies evolve
Verify persistent identifiers	Assign and maintain persistent identifiers such as DOIs for all datasets	Keeps references and citations stable even when systems, URLs, or platforms change
Create a crisis response plan	Maintain a written, tested plan defining responsibilities, escalation procedures, minimum service levels, and communication protocols and conduct post-incident reviews after disruptions	Transforms crisis response from improvisation into preparation, and turns experience into institutional learning

Conclusion

Data repositories are under pressure. Across the globe, the systems that store, maintain, and provide access to scientific and public data are navigating an unprecedented combination of challenges (funding instability, workforce loss, political disruption, and technical fragility) often simultaneously and without adequate support. This project set out to understand how those pressures are being experienced by the people closest to repositories, and what the community can do to strengthen them.

What emerged from focus groups, the survey, and Repository Crisis Scorecards submissions was a consistent and interconnected picture. Most repositories are performing reasonably well under normal conditions, but are significantly less prepared for disruption. Funding instability was the most frequently cited threat, affecting not just operations but staffing, planning, and long-term sustainability. Workforce loss compounds that vulnerability, when experienced staff leave with institutional knowledge, user relationships, and technical judgment that documentation alone cannot replace. And while many repositories have invested in strong day-to-day technical infrastructure, far fewer have formalized the crisis response plans, continuity agreements, and distributed partnerships that determine what happens when something goes wrong. These three challenges are interconnected, and addressing only one without the others leaves repositories exposed.

Across all three disruption themes, the community identified a core set of strategies that make repositories more resilient. Diversifying funding streams, building redundancy into data storage and infrastructure, and establishing crisis response plans before they are needed were among the most consistently cited. Investing in stable and well-supported staff, cross-training and succession planning, and securing formal partnerships and continuity agreements rounded out the picture. The most resilient repositories in this project were those that had addressed funding, people, and infrastructure together. The considerations that follow are organized by audience, because different groups have different roles to play in building resilient data ecosystems.

Recommendations for repository administrators:

- **Resilience is a system-wide responsibility:** Considerations for staff, governance, documentation, and financial planning matter as much as how the servers are managed
- **Build redundancy before it is needed:** tested backups, geographically distributed storage, and crisis response plans that exist before a disruption occurs
- **Plan for the loss of people, not just systems:** cross-training, succession planning, and documented workflows reduce the risk that any single departure creates a crisis
- **Identify successor hosts and transition plans now:** the platform or institution supporting a repository today may not be there tomorrow

Recommendations for data users:

- **Do not assume online availability means long-term access:** repository reliability can shift quickly and with little warning
- **Maintain local copies and document dependencies:** knowing where your data came from and having alternatives identified in advance protects your work
- **Recognize that citation and deposits are acts of support:** repositories make the case for continued investment through evidence of use
- **Treat data stewardship as part of the research process:** good science does not end at publication; the data underlying research should be preserved and accessible so others can verify, reproduce, and build on it

Recommendations for citizen archivists:

- **Work in coordination rather than in isolation:** communities of practice amplify individual contributions into something more systematic
- **Prioritize collectively:** sharing knowledge about which datasets are most at risk and least backed up elsewhere reduces duplication of effort and increases impact
- **Build relationships with repository administrators in advance:** those connections make rescue efforts more targeted and allow archivists to become part of a repository's resilience plan before a crisis hits

Recommendations for funders & policy makers:

- **Move toward multi-year funding commitments:** short-term grants create exactly the instability that makes repositories fragile
- **Protect data collection, not just preservation:** datasets that stop being updated quickly become obsolete, and the expertise needed to maintain them disappears with the funding
- **Pair policy with resources:** legislation without accompanying funding and staffing does not translate into implementation
- **Address regulatory barriers to international replication:** data sovereignty and cross-border governance frameworks shape whether distributed resilience strategies can work in practice

The strategies documented here emerged from the people closest to these challenges. They are not a prescription. What works for a large federally funded repository may not work for a small disciplinary archive. What is feasible in one country may be legally or financially impossible in another. These findings offer a starting point, a set of evidence-based considerations for anyone working to strengthen repository resilience in their own context.

Participant Perspectives: *We Can't Keep Everything, so What Should We Keep?*

Storage is not infinite, and neither are the resources required to maintain it. Energy, water, infrastructure, and the specialized labor needed to keep data accessible all come at a cost. Yet conversations about data preservation often proceed as though these limits do not exist, as though the answer to every threat is simply to save more, store more, and preserve more. At some point, difficult decisions have to be made about what to keep.

What makes this genuinely hard is that we cannot always know in advance which data will matter. When 18th-century British Navy ships logged detailed weather observations for navigation and national security, no one was thinking about climate science. Centuries later, those logs are foundational to modern climate models. The data that seems routine today may be exactly what someone needs in fifty years. And the data we decide is not worth keeping may turn out to be irreplaceable.

Future Considerations

Throughout this six-month project, deliberate efforts were made to engage a broad range of participants; however, some voices proved harder to reach than anticipated. Their absence shapes what can and cannot be concluded from these findings.

Citizen archivists were significantly underrepresented, with only two RCS completions and one focus group among this population. Operational and crisis response users (those who depend on real-time data to make decisions that can be life-saving) made up just 4% of survey respondents. Leaders in Indigenous data sovereignty, community scientists, and policymakers who use data to inform decisions were largely absent as well. Future iterations of this project should make deliberate efforts to reach these groups, both because their experiences of data disruption are likely very different from those of academic and research users, and because their perspectives change the conversation in important ways.

The citizen archivist focus group offered a striking example of this. While most participants across the project identified duplication of repositories as a problem to be solved (an inefficiency that wastes resources and fragments the ecosystem), the citizen archivists saw it differently. In their experience, redundancy is not a bug. It is a feature. Repositories that appear to duplicate each other's functions provide backup capacity when one fails, overlapping expertise when staff depart, and alternative access routes when a system goes offline. The COVID-19 pandemic offers a parallel: governments that had cut health system capacity in the name of efficiency found themselves without the surge capacity they needed when crisis struck. The same logic applies to data infrastructure. Efficiency and resilience are not always the same goal, and designing for one can undermine the other.

"So like that, that whole diversity ecosystem, having that multiplicity of approaches, I think, is probably the main thing if we look back that's going to have got us through this period."

- Focus Group Participant, on the need for implementing diverse mitigation strategies

This tension does not invalidate the recommendations in this paper. But it is a reminder that the strategies most effective at scale may create their own vulnerabilities over time, and that the community needs diverse perspectives to build resilience that actually holds.

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